

***Trichoderma grossum* looks better than *T. cornu-damae* as the scientific name of the widely distributed lethal fungus “Poison Fire Coral / 火焰茸 / カエンタケ”**

Kun L. Yang (mugoture@gmail.com; College of Forestry and Landscape Architecture, South China Agricultural University, Guangzhou 510642, Guangdong, China)

Jia Y. Lin (mycofloscula@gmail.com; College of Plant Protection, South China Agricultural University, Guangzhou 510642, Guangdong, China)

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Text

Having noticed the recent addition of the binomial combination *Trichoderma grossum* Samuels (2024) in Index Fungorum, we were motivated to prepare this communication.

粗木霉 *Trichoderma grossum* (Berk.) Samuels, *Mycotaxon* 137 (4 Suppl.): 256 (2024) [2022]

≡ 粗肉座菌 *Hypocrea grossa* Berk., *Hooker's journal of botany and Kew Garden Miscellany* 3: 206 (1851)

= 滇肉棒菌 *Podostroma yunnanense* M. Zang [as “yunnanensis”], *Materiae ad Diagnosis Fungorum Oeconomicarum Yunnanicum* II: 2 (1976)

= (?) 红角肉棒菌 (丛生肉棒菌、鹿角状肉棒菌) *Podostroma cornu-damae* (Pat.) Boedijn, *Bulletin du Jardin botanique de Buitenzorg, Sér. 3* 13: 274 (1934) (≡ 红角肉座菌 (丛生肉座菌、鹿角状肉座菌) *Hypocrea cornu-damae* Pat., in Patouillard & Lagerheim, *Société botanique et mycologique de France* 11 (4): 198 (1895); ≡ 红角木霉 (丛生木霉、鹿角状木霉) *Trichoderma cornu-damae* (Pat.) Z.X. Zhu & W.Y. Zhuang, *Mycosystema* 33 (6): 1207 (2014))

An ascomycete with conspicuous reddish stromata, frequently cited as *Trichoderma cornu-damae* (dubbed Poison Fire Coral / 火焰茸 / カエンタケ) and known to be not only fatal when ingested but also risky upon contact by its toxin irritating to skin and mucous membranes, has been widely reported across East and Southeast Asia (e.g., Saikawa *et al.* 2001, Ahn *et al.* 2013, Yang *et al.* 2013, Kim *et al.* 2016, Lee *et al.* 2019, Ohta *et al.* 2021, Putra *et al.* 2022; sometimes even reported in farther regions like Oceania as well). Available molecular evidence from GenBank (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>) looks consistent with this point, as the following

sequences from ITS locus across collections from distant regions are nearly identical*: AB509797 (Ex-“Epitype of *Trichoderma cornu-damae*” NBRC9005 = IFO9005 = G.J.S.06-03 from Japan, cf. Bissett *et al.* 2015), OM149710 (BO24623 from Indonesia, cf. Putra *et al.* 2022), KP004943 (ASIS24940 from South Korea, cf. Seok *et al.* unpublished), PX415258 (HTBM3134A from China, sequenced by us), and PX415259 (HTBM3134B from China, sequenced by us) (*Therefore, the problem that the ITS locus was suggested as unsatisfactory in microspecies delimitation (Cai & Druzhinina 2021) is not considered here; same below). This species nests in a subclade (sometimes referred to as *lbrevicomactum* clade) sister to the one containing the type of *Trichoderma* (e.g., Cai & Druzhinina 2021, Wang *et al.* 2024). However, it is notable that the type locality of *Trichoderma cornu-damae* (\equiv *Hypocrea cornu-damae* Pat. 1895) is in a high-land area in Southwest China (around the Kangding City, Ganzi Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Sichuan Province, elevation about 2,500 m, cf. Patouillard 1895, Tang *et al.* unpublished), but no sequenced collections from this region are available.

▲ **Figure 1.** Currently accepted *Trichoderma grossum* (photos by Kun L. Yang). (a–e, l–m) Holotype of *Podostroma yunnanense* (HKAS000038) (d. Mature asci; e. Longitudinal section of stroma pellis; l. Stroma surface covered by masses of part-ascospores; m. Part-ascospores, also cited in Tang *et al.* unpublished); (f–k) HTBM3134 from East China collected in 2025, with ITS sequences available from PX415258 & PX415259 (f. Longitudinal section of a perithecium, mature asci not observed; g. Longitudinal section of stroma pellis; h. Do not imitate this action, as it is potentially risky for someone when contacting this fungus — See also うごめ紀 @Youtube available from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PXmveVaHBuU> (accessed on September 25, 2025) —Do not believe? Why were there such ethnomycological records present before the scientific confirmation of its toxicity irritating to skin and mucous membranes?).

There are two other legitimate but less known names describing species similar to *Hypocrea cornu-damae* Pat. 1895, one proposed later (*Podostroma yunnanense* M. Zang 1976 from Lüchun County, Honghe Hani and Yi Autonomous Prefecture, Yunnan Province, elevation about 1,900 m, cf. Sporophyte Group of Taxonomy Division & Fungus Group of Physiology Division 1976), and the other earlier (*Hypocrea grossa* Berk. 1851 from Darjeeling, East India, elevation probably between that of *P. yunnanense* and *H. cornu-damae*, cf. Berkeley 1851). Chamberlain *et al.* (2004) noted a comparison between *H. cornu-damae* and *H. grossa* based on type studies, that the stroma pellis is trending pseudoparenchymatous in *H. grossa* but composed of filamentous elements in *H. cornu-damae*, and the ascospore ornamentation is less distinct in *H. cornu-damae* than in *H. grossa*. Kun L. Yang re-examined the holotype of *Podostroma yunnanense* (HKAS000038), consistent with Wang & Liu (2002), found it generally showing the typical features of *H. grossa* (Figure 1). Kun L. Yang further examined a collection made in East China, which would be identified as *Hypocrea cornu-damae* following traditions, found it possessing typical features of *H. grossa* as well (Figure 1). Accompanied with Tang *et al.* (unpublished), who studied the ITS sequence of holotype of *P. yunnanense* (HKAS000038) and found it nearly identical with KP004943 (ASIS24940 from South Korea, cf. Seok *et al.* unpublished, labeled as *P. cornu-damae*), it now looks evident that *P. yunnanense* is safely a later synonym of *Hypocrea grossa*, and that the widely distributed so-called *Trichoderma cornu-damae* is morphologically the same as *H. grossa* but different from the true *T. cornu-damae*. Therefore, it looks ideal and safe to displace *T. cornu-damae* with *T. grossum* for the famous widely distributed lethal fungus "Poison Fire Coral / 火焰茸 / カエンタケ"; and even if *T. cornu-damae* is finally also confirmed as conspecific with *T. grossum*, the latter still holds priority.

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